

Manufacturing and Assembly of Modular and Reusable EV Battery for Environment-Friendly and Lightweight Mobility

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Abstract. Range anxiety is one of the key reasons why Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) market still has not fully taken off. Users demand EV to be able to fast-charge and travel long distances with short breaks. Ultra-Fast charge appears, therefore, as one of the milestones to reach for widespread electrification. However, such amounts of power, even during short time, require of a proper dimensioning of the system. Thus, the battery must be prepared for such events, controlling cell status during operation to drop the effect of both fast battery degradation and potential dangerous events. Consequently, an increased battery performance requires an adapted battery thermal management system (BTMS) to ensure a uniform temperature distribution in the battery pack especially during fast and ultra-fast charging, to ensure the longest possible battery lifetime. In this paper, the influence of different thermal conductivities of the BTMS on the average battery cell temperature are investigated. The simulation bases on a hybrid 3D/1D model of a module which enables an easy comparison of the impact of the thermal conductivity of the battery cell, thermal pads, heat spreader, and the cooling channels design. The results can be used to determine which measurements have a particularly high influence on the performance of the cooling system. Furthermore, it is possible to identify potential to reduce the weight of the system and keep the environmental impact as low as possible.

Keywords: Battery thermal management · cell ageing · lightweight mobility · simulation · electric vehicle

1 Introduction

BEV are the key technology to decarbonise road transport, a sector that accounts for around 16% of global emissions. To accelerate the introduction of BEVs into the mass market, the MARBEL project was launched to develop an ultra-high-performance battery for cars with a higher energy density, shorter and more efficient fast charging, and a longer lifetime [1]. Lithium-ion batteries are used to achieve the required energy density [2]. Since the performance, safety and lifespan of the battery cells are affected by their operating temperature a BTMS is needed to keep the operating temperature within a range of 15–35 °C with a maximum temperature spread of 5 K at battery cell level [3, 4]. The most common systems rely on air-based, liquid-based, phase change material, heat-pipe based BTMS or a combination of these [5]. This allows to combine the advantages of each system.

2 Thermal Management System

The battery pack consists of 32 modules which contains 12 battery cells each. In Fig. 1 an explosion view of the module thermal management system without the housing is shown. On the top of the battery cell are the welded aluminum terminals that serve as both electrical and thermal connection. The side compression pad absorbs the volume change of the battery cell during the lifetime and ensures uniform pretension. On the opposite side the L-shaped aluminum fin distributes the thermal energy across the surface and dissipates it downward to the cooling plate. Thermal pads are placed between the battery cell and the fin to reduce thermal resistance and compensate the tolerances. This described design represents the smallest increment of the thermal management system (TMS).

Fig. 1. Explosion view of the module thermal management system. Reproduced with permission from [AVL Deutschland GmbH], copyright [AVL Deutschland GmbH], [2024].

For the module, the battery cells with the compression pads, the compression and thermal pads and the fins are stacked and connected to the busbars. On top of them there is a cover plate with thermal pads on both sides to provide a good thermal conductivity between the water-cooled top cooling plates and the busbars. With this design it is possible to dissipate the heat generated by the busbars and the terminals into the top cooling plates and reduce the temperature spread within the battery cell [6]. As with conventional cooling systems, there is also another water-cooled plate with a thermal pad on the bottom of the battery cell stack. With this design the cooling channels are integrated in the battery pack housing to integrate two functions in one part to achieve the weight goals.

3 3D Simulation of the TMS

A 3D conjugate heat transfer computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation was performed with the software STAR-CCM+ using a steady Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) approach. For the coolant flow a 2nd order numerical scheme was used together with a K-epsilon turbulence model. The near wall regime was treated with a two-layer approach to resolve the boundary layer effects. In the solid parts the energy equation is solved together with an additional source term to include the ohmic joule heating due to electric current flows at the busbars and terminals also using 2nd order numerical scheme. An average mesh size of 2–4 mm is employed to resolve the thermal paths using polyhedral and thin prismatic finite volume numerical cells. The analysis of the temperature distribution is performed for one module and considers a heat release of 10 W per battery cell (2C charge). An electrical contact resistance of 25 μ Ohm between the busbar and the terminal is considered. The flow rate of the cooling medium is symmetrical and is 2.03 l/min for the upper and lower cooling plate. The starting temperature is 25 °C for the battery cell and the coolant. Table 1 summarizes the material parameters used.

Table 1. 3D simulation parameters

Part	Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific heat (J/kgK)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)
Battery cell	-	2100	1100	5/20/12 (x/y/z)
Terminal	Aluminium	2700	f(t)	180
Busbar	Copper	8960	f(t)	401
Compression pad	Aerogel	350	400	f(t) (0,02–0,09)
Thermal pad	Silicon	2100	2000	3
Fin	Aluminium	2700	f(t)	180
Cover plate	Aluminium	2700	f(t)	180
Cooling plate	Aluminium	2700	f(t)	180

For a better assessment of the temperature distribution, Fig. 2 shows an exploded view of the smallest increment of the cooling system in a steady case. The cold spots of the battery cell are located on the poles and on the underside. Due to the fin, the temperature distribution on the left side is more homogeneous than on the right. This is where the highest temperature is found. Due to the combination of a top and bottom cooling concept, the maximum temperature spread does not exceed 5 K in the battery cell and is smaller than 5 K in the whole pack when the average battery cell temperature is considered.

Fig. 2. Temperature distribution in one battery cell of the module simulated with STAR CCM+

4 Model Order Reduction

To increase the computational speed and to investigate the influence of different parameters on the battery cell temperature, a 1D simulation of the battery cell is combined with a 3D thermal simulation. The basis is the model developed by Guitart et al. which has good agreement with the practical experiments and the 3D simulations from Sect. 3 [7]. The starting temperature of the simulation is 26.5 °C for the module and 20 °C for the coolant with a total flow rate of 4.06 l/min (Table 2).

The parameters represent a maximum approach with high thermal conductivities (HC) of the thermal pads and fin material. For the thermal conductivity of the battery cell 20% higher values are considered. In the simulation the different parameters are varied individually to determine the effects on the average temperature. In a further simulation, the cooling channels are modified (Fig. 4). Finally, the parameters with the largest impact on the mean battery cell temperature are combined to investigate the potential of the TMS. In Fig. 3 the average battery cell temperature is shown with the error indicators visualizing the minimum and maximum battery cell temperature in the whole module.

Table 2. Variation of simulation parameter for case study

Part	Low thermal conductivity (W/mK)	High thermal conductivity (W/mK)
Battery cell	5/20/12 (x/y/z)	6/24/14,5 (x/y/z)
Thermal pad	3	20
Fin	180 (Aluminium)	401 (Copper)

Fig. 3. Temperature evolution with different simulation parameters

The standard case represents the simulation with the low thermal conductivities and with the standard cooling channels. A higher thermal conductivity of the thermal pads does not decrease the average battery cell temperature significantly. With the copper fins the average battery cell temperature in the module can be reduced by 0,71 K with a more homogeneous temperature distribution at battery cell level. The high thermal conductivity battery cell has a lower impact on the average battery cell temperature while the temperature spread remains the same. When the number of cooling channels is increased as shown in Fig. 4 the average battery cell temperature is decreased by 1,01 K but increases the temperature spread at battery cell level.

Fig. 4. Cooling channel, standard layout (left) and optimized (right)

With the combination of the high fin thermal conductivity and the optimized cooling channel design the average battery cell temperature can be decreased by 1,70 K which corresponds the linear add-up of both measures. The temperature spread on battery cell level is also the lowest compared to the other setups (7,06 K).

5 Discussion

Thermal pads have the smallest influence on the average battery cell temperature and are not the bottleneck in the TMS. The higher thermal conductivity does not lead to a higher temperature difference between the coolant and the fin and therefore does not enhance the cooling performance. This effect can be reached by a thicker fin, or a material with higher thermal conductivity like copper. Due to the higher temperature difference of the bottom of the fin to the coolant, more energy is transferred. On the contrary, this leads to an earlier increase of the coolant temperature, which results in a higher temperature spread within the module. This can be countered with an adapted fin thickness, if thin fins are used at the cold side of the module with gradually increasing thickness towards the warm side. The increase of the battery cell thermal conductivity has a less significant impact on the temperature spread within the module, compared to the fins and shows the relevance of further increasing thermal conductivity. Apart from the thermal conductivity of the TMS components, the simulation points out the importance of the cooling channel design. By dividing large cooling channels into smaller ones, a lower average battery cell temperature can be achieved for the same installation space. The heat transfer to the cooling medium is the bottleneck in this TMS design. In the standard case, the energy dissipated from the battery cell cannot be transferred to the fluid, which results in the higher average battery cell temperature and a bigger temperature spread within the module. At the same time, the temperature spread within the module remains comparatively small, which also supports this conclusion. For future TMS, it is an option to adapt the heat transfer by different cooling channel designs and to achieve a lower and more uniform temperature distribution in the battery pack. The combination of the higher thermal conductivity and the optimized cooling channel design leads to the lowest average battery cell temperatures with the highest temperature spread within the module. Adjustment of the heat transfer or fin thickness is required to achieve a more homogeneous temperature distribution in the pack.

The results shown are valid for the TMS presented.

6 Conclusion

In the paper it can be shown that with a calibrated hybrid simulation model the influences of the elements of the TMS can be investigated to reduce the battery cell temperature and spread. The influence of the thickness and thermal conductivity of the thermal pads is small in absolute terms. A higher thermal conductivity or thickness of the fins reduces the average battery cell temperature. For a homogeneous temperature distribution in the pack, different thicknesses of the fins should be used. The heat transfer of the coolant has the greatest influence on the battery cell temperature and can be controlled by the geometry of the cooling channels. With an adapted cooling channel design, the temperature and the temperature spread inside the battery pack can be controlled and will decrease the aging of the battery cells for a longer lifetime of the whole battery pack.

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